

THE CONTRIBUTION OF WOMEN SCIENTISTS OF CENTRAL ASIA TO THE SCIENTIFIC DEVELOPMENT OF MODERN HYDRAULIC ACCUMULATORS

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Annotation. This article covers scientific and technological developments across the countries of Central Asia, updating high-tech projects, applying scientific and practical recommendations to production, as well as many important aspects of scientific research conducted by women scientists, including the creation of hydraulic accumulators. and scientific developments of their design. Significant successful achievements in manufacturing are recognized.

Keywords: Hydraulic battery, electricity, environment, Water batteries, discharge, Corrosion.

ВКЛАД ЖЕНЩИН УЧЕНЫХ ЦЕНТРАЛЬНОЙ АЗИИ В НАУЧНУЮ РАЗРАБОТКУ СОВРЕМЕННЫХ ГИДРАВЛИЧЕСКИХ АККУМУЛЯТОРОВ

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Аннотация. В этой статье научно-технические разработки в масштабах стран Центральной Азии, актуализация наукоемких проектов, применение научных и практических рекомендаций к производству, а также многие важные аспекты научных исследований, проводимых женщинами-учеными, в том числе создание гидроаккумуляторов. и научные разработки их конструкции. Признаны значительные успешные достижения в области производства.

Ключевые слова: Гидробатарея, электричество, окружающая среда, Водяные батареи, разряд, Коррозия.

INTRODUCTION

The development of the scientific personnel training system was an important factor in the formation of the new Uzbekistan. The Ministry of Innovative Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Fund for the Support of Innovative Development and Innovative Ideas was established, the Law "On Science and Scientific Activity" was adopted, in which scientific creativity and freedom of information, efficiency and creative competition provided. defined as one of the main principles of the field of science and scientific activity. More than 700 female doctors of science and six academicians work in scientific and educational institutions of our republic. In our country, the interest and activity of women in scientific research, they have a leading role in the development of new ideas of Uzbekistan.

At the level of Central Asian countries, scientific and technical developments, updating of knowledge-intensive projects, application of scientific and practical recommendations to production, and many important aspects of scientific research conducted by women scientists, including the creation of hydro accumulators and their design in the field of scientific production significant achievements can be recognized.

It should be noted that women with intellectual and creative potential are still victims of persistent inequality or prejudice. As UNESCO Director-General Audrey Azoulay noted: *"Throughout history and to this day, science is one of the many fields where women have been*

forgotten. This situation leads to the continuation of inequality between women and men. UNESCO is fully committed to addressing this critical issue by working across the entire chain, from education to the collective representation of women in science. Above all, education as the foundation of all opportunities, focusing on girls and women, and urgently combating inequality in our education systems."

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Today, renowned women scientists from the Harbin Institute of Technology of the People's Republic of China have created and developed hydro batteries, that is, modern eco-friendly water-based water batteries (WB), which represent a promising alternative safe and scalable energy storage that meets modern consumer requirements with high power density and durability. It is appropriate to think about fuel energy that meets the requirements. Famous scientist B. Dunn and chief. Electric energy storage for the grid: selection battery in scientific papers Due to the depletion of resources and pollution caused by the burning of fossil fuels, the search for alternative clean energy is becoming a focus of research worldwide [1]. This has led to an increased demand for electrical energy storage, especially for advanced batteries with practical potential for grid-scale applications, and rechargeable lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) are of particular research interest.

However, despite their high energy density, this remains a common problem that hinders LIBs in safety-critical applications. Recent incidents include the 2013 Boeing 787 battery fire, the 2016 Samsung Note 7 explosion, and the 2019 Tesla Model S fire. These are serious threats to human health or life [2]. In addition, the low voltage and increasing cost of Li and Co also pose challenges for large-scale applications [3, 4], in the past, the development of sodium ion batteries (NIBs) and potassium ion batteries (KIBs), pilot, has been somewhat hindered for a decade due to safety concerns and environmental concerns due to the use of flammable and toxic organic electrolytes [5, 6]. The above-mentioned disadvantages of organic media have encouraged the pursuit of alternative advanced batteries where the systems can be used on a grid scale.

Water batteries (WB) are a relatively safer alternative. Also, the use of aqueous electrolytes provides greater competitiveness, with the exception of low cost, electrolyte and production costs, oxygen-free and desiccant assembly lines;

It is harmless to the environment due to the volatility, non-toxicity and non-flammability of water;

Fast charging ability and high power density due to the high ionic conductivity of the aqueous medium;

High tolerance to electrical and mechanical malfunctions, i.e. survival after rapid discharge, bending, cutting and washing without any fatal consequences.

Until now, various types of WB (Ni-Fe, Ni-Cd and Pb-acid SB) have been successfully produced, recently, due to material development and improvement of their electrochemical performance, it has been revived as one of WB. especially ideal candidates for large-scale energy storage. We also saw a dramatic increase in WB over the past 10 years (Figure 1, A and B).

Fig. 1. Status and challenges of current ABs. (A) Number of publications devoted to different ABs. Data were collected from Web of Science in October 2019. Inset numbers represent typical scale labels. (B) Classification of ABs. (C) Summary of key challenges that are limiting energy/power densities and life span of current acidic, near-neutral, and alkaline ABs. However, two common problems have hindered the grid-scale application of SB, namely limited energy density and unsatisfactory lifetime. Basically, water has a thermodynamic oxidation potential [oxygen evolution reaction (OER)] and a reduction potential [hydrogen evolution reaction (HER)], which are separated by a narrow window of 1.23 V. Water has a narrow electrochemical stability window (ESW) operating voltage (Fig. 2), which leads to insufficient energy density of SBs [7].

Fig. 2. Summary of electrolyte and electrode engineering strategies for the design of high-performance ABs.

Corrosion, passivation and other negative reactions during the process are closely related to the process and stability of the charge discharge. Corrosion (self-discharge) is an effective side reaction in strongly acidic or alkaline aqueous electrolytes, which not only reduces, but also leads to irreversible water consumption and electrolyte concentration changes. Corrosion of electrodes is usually present in ABs and usually occurs at the interface between the electrode surface and the electrolyte medium. Thus, the chemistry at the electrode-electrolyte interface plays a crucial role in protecting the electrode from corrosion. Interphase chemistry and corrosion mechanisms are closely related to the composition and physicochemical properties of the electrolyte and pH. Therefore, depending on these factors, different strategies have been used for certain systems, resulting in reduced zinc anode corrosion and improved battery performance. The main strategies published so far to reduce the corrosion rate of electrode materials include the addition of inorganic (e.g., Zn-Bi alloy and silica coating) or organic polyethylene glycol and polyaniline (PANI) coating corrosion to the electrode or electrolyte.

Fig. 3. Summary of advanced materials for Li/Na/K ion-based ABs. (A) Main progress in LiABs, NaABs, and KABs. (B) Summary of ESW of water and redox potentials of various electrode materials in organic LIBs, NIBs, and KIBs. (C) Illustration of the difference between Li⁺ solvation sheath in diluted and water-in-salt solutions. Reproduced with permission from the American Association for the Advancement of Science (27). (D) Schematic illustration of the conversion-intercalation mechanism occurring in the LBC-G composite in WIBS electrolyte. (E) Actual (red star) energy density of the LBC-G//G full cells compared with various state-of-the-art commercial and experimental Li-ion chemistries. (D) and (E) are reproduced with permission from the Nature Publishing Group (28).

In addition, aluminum is an abundant metal, cheap, chemically inert, and has the highest volume-specific charge storage capacity (8040 mA/h cm⁻³) as shown, which is about four times that of lithium metal batteries. The main problem of the aluminum anode is the rapid and

irreversible formation of a high bandwidth passivated oxide layer of Al_2O_3 . Archer and colleagues reviewed AlCl_3 -1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium chloride treated aluminum substrate and found that coating with this ionic liquid eroded the oxide film and protected the aluminum from further oxide film formation.

Conclusion

As promising energy storage systems for intermittent energy use and sustainable large-scale applications, advanced SBs, taking advantage of their low cost, ease of harvesting and processing of abundant resources, environmental friendliness, and above all, safety, are the future automotive and electric vehicles. capable of replacing traditional Li-ion, Ni-MH and Pb-acid batteries for hardware, scalable energy storage applications. In recent years, we have witnessed the rapid development of electrode materials with excellent electrochemical performance and new electrochemical mechanisms. Although significant progress has been made in this area, continuous efforts are needed to improve energy density and long-term stability before practical applications can be met. Next, an attempt is made to summarize and present the advantages and disadvantages of some SB systems, and the prospects for the next stage of SB development are currently LIB, Ni/MH, and lead-acid batteries. Rechargeable batteries, the energy storage systems available in the global market LIBs are all commercial power sources for portable electronics, electric vehicles and backup power sources and have seen their widespread use in recent decades.

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